

SUBJECT: ENSURING HARMONY OF CHILDREN'S PHYSICAL AND MENTAL DEVELOPMENT BASED ON RULED GAMES

Umarova Mehriniso Ibragim kizi

Teacher of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7347523>

Abstract: Games play an important role in education in preschool educational organizations. Play is an independent activity, an independent activity in which the child first begins to communicate with peers. For preschool children, play is very important: for them play is learning, for them play is work, for them play is a serious form of education.

Key words: Game, physical, mental, independent, work, education.

For preschool children, the game is a way to learn about the world around them. They are united by one goal, working together with its achievements, common interests and experiences. While playing, the child learns to use his knowledge, to be able to use it in various situations. In creative games, the child acquires new knowledge, skills and abilities. Games that contribute to the development of perception, attention, memory, thinking, creative abilities are generally aimed at the mental development of a preschool child. In creative games, children's imagination, making things, and experimenting open up a wide path.

1. games aimed at improving children's mental processes:

- mobile; - intellectual; - aesthetic.

2. technical games:

- art games; - agricultural games; - games related to profession; - construction games.

3. life-social games:

- about family life; - kindergarten, school; - related to social life; - socio-political games;

4. military games:

- "Soldier-soldier" game; - "Sailor (sailor)" game.

5. Dramatized games:

- theater; - cinema; - circus.

Children's games of preschool age D.B. Elkonin, in turn, classified as follows:

- games related to the plot of a household theme; - games related to the production plot; - games with a socio-political plot.

The scope of the plot of the game can be expanded by properly organizing educational influence on children. When a child arrives at a pre-school educational institution, their games reflect only the events of family life. games such as train, hairdressing, salesmanship will be added. The increase in children's games is also explained by their age characteristics. As children grow up, the plot of their games becomes richer and more diverse. All games of preschool children are divided into two large categories according to their content, characteristics and organization:

1. Creative games. 2. Games with rules.

Creative games are invented by children themselves. There will be no predetermined rules. Rules are invented by children during the game. The content and rules of games with rules are determined by adults. These rules must be followed during the game.

For creative games:

- plot role-playing games; - staged games; - includes building and crafting games.

Children's impressions of their surroundings are reflected in creative games. Such games are an independent game, the content of which is invented by the participants themselves. In this game, the child's freedom, independence, organizational and creative abilities are fully demonstrated. In the game, life impressions are not exactly reflected, but they are reworked in the minds of children and applied to the game. This is manifested in the child's creation of the idea of the game, the creation of its content, and the choice of descriptive tools. The child's impressions from the life around him - from the activities of his peers and adults - are processed, supplemented and qualitatively changed in creative games. Such children's games are a practical form of knowing the surrounding existence.

Role-playing games are reflective activities by their nature. Role-playing games increase children's observation, curiosity, and develop their knowledge. In his game, the child experiences one or another emotion related to the content of his role, which reflects existence. In role-playing games, each child plays the role assigned to him. For example, a builder, a driver, an educator, a nanny, a teacher. In story role-playing games, children first play in small groups of 2-3 people. In large and preparatory groups, they unite into a large number of teams. Friendly relations are formed in the game. When the child reaches the age of five, the observation of the child increases even more compared to the age of 3-4, his thinking develops and the range of knowledge expands. Because of this, the content of the game becomes more complicated. Through the development of imagination, games are played on the content of fairy tales and stories. At the age of senior kindergarten, creative games develop very well. In these games, children begin to fully apply the knowledge, skills, and emotions they have received from the events, stories, books, and other sources they have heard and seen. Long-lasting games are the highest stage of preschool children's games. If the games of children of the age group are properly guided, their strong team will be formed. In role-playing games, children use various tools. In the course of the game, they name some things as they wish and play hypothetically. For example, they take sand for sugar, a chair for a car, and grains for candy. The more reflective media, the richer the content of the game. Psychologist J. Piaget paid serious attention to the factor of giving new names to objects in the game and came to the conclusion that this work is the basis of symbolic and meaningful forms of imagination. During the game, the child develops as a person. According to the research conducted by well-known pedagogic scientists, by correctly leading children's games in all aspects, they will learn the content, organization, structure of the game, moral relations between children, and the development and improvement of the games. you can see the secret.

The second group of children's games are games with rules. This includes:

- didactic; - mobile; - musical; - fun games.

Games with rules, like all games, are practical activities. But children are required to follow the established rule. Established rules teach children to be responsible. The child learns to work together in a team and compromise with others. Each game with rules has its own idea and content. During the game, the correct implementation of the rules is determined by the

grades "correct" or "incorrect", "the rule of the game is violated". Children learn self-control during play. Of course, at the end of each game, the result should be discussed by the educator, the goal, rules and results should be paid attention to. Encouraging the participants at the end of the game, praising the active participants - ensures the effective passage of future games. All the above-mentioned types of games with rules have their own rules according to the content. They have the following characteristics:

- the existence of a game task performed through game actions;
- actions and relationships of players are guided by rules;
- presence of rules and ready content in the game;
- the educational content of the game is embodied in the events of the game actions, which do not appear as an independent task for children.

The uniqueness of the children's game is that it reflects the surrounding life, the activities, work, actions of winters, and their interactions in the work process. During the game, the house can be the sea, forest, subway, railway carriage for children. A child never plays silently, even if he plays alone, he talks to the toy, communicates with the character he is portraying, speaks instead of his mother, the patient, the doctor, and so on. . The word helps to reveal the image better.

The teacher's mastery of the method of leading the game process is the main condition for successful games. Selection and planning of action games is carried out according to the program.

References:

1. Umarova Mekhriniso "The use of creative games in the educational process in preschool education" Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal <https://wos.academiascience.org>. Published: May 19, 2022.
2. Umarova, M. (2022). CHARACTERISTICS OF EDUCATION OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE SPIRIT OF MORAL VALUES. Physical and technological education, 4(4). izvlecheno ot <https://history.jdpu.uz/index.php/phys-tech/article/view/6538>
3. Kuvvatova, M. H., & Alisherova, S. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF VOCABULARY WORK IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPEECH OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 2(3), 472-474. izvlecheno ot <https://www.in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/1498>
4. Mahira Kuvvatova Hikmatullaevna. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CREATIVITY AS A PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. Galaxy International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research, 10(10), 571-574. Retrieved from <https://internationaljournals.co.in/index.php/giirj/article/view/2660>
5. Salomov R.S. Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va uslubiyati. Darslik. T.: «ITA-PRESS», 2014. 269 bet.
6. Salomov RS., Sharipov A.K. Jismoniy tarbiya nazariyasi va uslubiyati. Darslik. T.: «ITA-PRESS», 2015.182 bet.
7. Goncharova O.V. "Yosh sportchilarning jismoniy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish" o'quv qo'llanma T.: O'zDJTI nashriyoti 2005 y.